

Enhancing Student Engagement and Assessment

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Abstract

In engineering education, fostering active student engagement and effective assessment strategies is crucial for enhancing learning outcomes. This study explores innovative teaching and assessment methods implemented in engineering courses involving around 500 students across multiple engineering degree programs. To promote active learning, we incorporated peer assessment and collaborative group work, where students completed structured tasks evaluated through detailed rubrics. In theoretical classes, we introduced Vevox, an interactive response system, to increase student participation and comprehension. Additionally, board games were integrated into selected topics to enhance conceptual understanding through gamification. Assessment methods were diversified to ensure comprehensive evaluation. Throughout the semester, students completed online tests via Moodle, allowing for continuous assessment and immediate feedback. A final written examination was conducted at the end of the term to assess overall knowledge retention and application. The impact of these strategies was measured by comparing student performance with the previous academic year. Results indicate a significant improvement, with an increase of 14% in the number of approved students. Feedback from students highlighted increased motivation, deeper understanding of theoretical concepts, and greater engagement with course material. These findings demonstrate that a combination of interactive learning tools, peer assessment, and varied evaluation methods can significantly enhance engineering education. This study provides some insights for educators seeking to implement innovative approaches that foster deeper learning and improve student outcomes in STEM disciplines.

Keywords: active-learning, calculus, peer-assessment, gamification.

1 Introduction

Active learning prepares students for the challenges of the future by equipping them with the skills and competencies needed in the modern workforce. Employers increasingly value graduates who can think critically, solve complex problems, and work effectively in teams. By incorporating active learning strategies into university curricula, educators can help students develop these essential skills and better prepare them for their future careers. A definition of active learning is given in (Freeman, et al., 2014) "Active learning engages students in the process of learning through activities and/or discussion in class, as opposed to passively listening to an expert. It emphasizes higher-order thinking and often involves group work."

Being Calculus a first year and first semester curricular unit for science and engineering students, it is a good starting point to shift the way students learn and collaborate. In this paper we will present the strategies used to engage students and discuss the results of this practice.

Moodle is the Learning Management System used in University of Aveiro. It has a great potential to work with active learning methodologies, namely submitting and classifying group work, peer assessment tools, bank of questions that can be reused, the facility of creating online tests, of communicating, etc. These features, along with its generalised use in our university, made us choose it as the communication platform in our course.

In the first class of the semester, we explained to the students how the Calculus course would work, what was expected of them, and most importantly, we justified the importance of the methods we would use.

We could define three fundamental axes of the methodology used: Communication, not only mathematical communication; Assessment and Learning activities.

To promote communication between students, group work was implemented along 12 sessions during the semester. It is our belief that “the more time students spend working in groups, the more favourable their learning-related attitudes become” (Springer, Stanne, & Donovan, 1999).

The same authors support that “The rationale for implementing group goals is that, if students value the success of the group, they will encourage and help one another to achieve” (Springer, Stanne, & Donovan, 1999).

Assessment is the thickest axe, because most students fight for the grades, although with different targets: just approval or the best grades in class.

Assessment is the making of judgements about how students’ work meets appropriate standards. Teachers, markers and examiners have traditionally been charged with that responsibility. However, students themselves need to develop the capacity to make judgements about both their own work and that of others in order to become effective continuing learners and practitioners.

As referred in (Boud, 2010),

- assessment should be used to engage students in productive learning;
- feedback should be used to actively improve student learning;
- students and teachers become responsible partners in learning and assessment;
- students should be involved in assessment practices;
- learning assessment should be placed at the heart of subject conception and programme design;
- learning assessment should promote institutional and individual development;
- assessment should provide an inclusive and reliable representation of student performance.

These principles were the drivers of the assessment process we designed.

An example of learning activities developed in our Calculus course was the use of instructional board games, as they can be a powerful tool in mathematics teaching for university students. They offer a dynamic and engaging way to explore complex mathematical concepts, fostering both understanding and retention.

In section 2 we will describe in detail the instruments used along the course and in section 3 we will focus on discussion of results compared with previous academic years.

2 Methods

At the University of Aveiro, Calculus is part of the curriculum of almost all the sciences and engineering degrees, but students are enrolled on different Calculus courses: our unit has around 500 students from Physics, Biomedical Engineering, Computational Engineering, Physical Engineering, Meteorology, Oceanography, and Climate, Materials Engineering, Industrial Engineering and Management and Mechanical Engineering.

Our Calculus course has four weekly contact hours divided into two blocks of two hours each. These hours were used to discuss the theoretical concepts relevant to the course, supplemented with examples and one or two in-class exercises (2 hours, usually 1 hour in each lecture); to do group work, where the teacher acted as a guide (1 hour) and address student queries and clarify issues identified in the previously submitted group work (1 hour).

To make the lectures more dynamic and interactive, especially when discussing or presenting new concepts, we utilized Vevox for posing questions to students, whose responses were then discussed collectively.

Having in mind that this is a first year, first semester curricular unit, students were explained the objectives of the course, beginning with the non-mathematical ones: promote relationships among students; encourage group work, embracing differences; develop work habits both inside and outside the classroom; foster healthy discussions among students and between students and teachers and hold each student accountable for their own learning.

They were also told that they would integrate three different groups throughout the semester, randomly formed using a Moodle tool. This approach promotes interaction with various peers, fostering a crucial skill for future professional life.

In the following we describe the various components of the course.

2.1 Working in groups

Working in groups helps students develop stronger communication skills, as they need to explain their ideas, listen to others and provide feedback.

Weekly, students completed a group task (each group had different tasks but with the same educational content) on the topics covered in that class and/or the previous class. These tasks were submitted on Moodle at the end of the class for evaluation by the teacher. An example of a submitted task is in Figure 1.

	Cálculo I - B	TPA11-E	2024/25
Critérios da razão, da raiz e de Leibniz. Séries de Potências			
Indicar a turma <input type="text" value="TPB-"/> e o grupo <input type="text" value="G-"/> e preencher com os dados dos elementos do grupo presentes:			
Papel atribuído	N.º Mec.	Nome	
Gestor/Portavoz	_____	_____	
Escreva/Carteiro	_____	_____	
Colaborador	_____	_____	
Antes de o anexar, verificar que o ficheiro PDF tem boa qualidade!			
1. Estuda a natureza da série $\sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-3)^n}{1+n3^n}$ e, caso seja convergente, especifica se simples ou absolutamente.			
2. Determina, em função do parâmetro α , a natureza (convergente simples/absolutamente ou divergente) da série $\sum_{n=1}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{n\alpha}{n+\alpha^2}\right)^n$ com $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$.			
3. Considera a série de potências $S(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n+1}}{2n+1}$.			
(a) Determine a natureza da série para $x = -1, x = 1$ e $x = 2$.			
(b) Determine o domínio de convergência da série, indicando os pontos onde a convergência é simples e onde é absoluta.			
Resolução			

Figure 1. Example of a task students had to submit after solving the exercises.

The page header contains the name of the course (*Cálculo I – B*), the assignment title (TPA means Task for Lecture) and the curricular topic (*Critérios da razão, da raiz e de Leibniz. Séries de Potências* - Ratio, Root, and Leibniz Criteria. Power Series).

The students had to fill the fields class TPB_ and group G_ and then the list of the students of the group that were present in that specific lecture. The group had to choose, in each task, who was going to be the manager/spokesperson (although they didn't respect a lot this mandate) and the writer/postman, i.e., the student who had to write and submit on Moodle the detailed answer. The others were collaborators. The only acceptable format for submission was PDF, and they had the warning "Before sending, check that the PDF file is of good quality!" Figure 2 shows an example of a submitted and corrected task.

The assignments were evaluated using the rubrics described in table 1, which the students knew from the beginning of the semester. Rubrics are a powerful tool in education that enhance clarity, fairness, and efficiency in the grading process, while also providing valuable feedback and promoting student self-assessment and reflection. "A rubric is a coherent set of criteria for student work that includes descriptions of the quality levels of performance according to the criteria" (Brookhart, 2013).

Figure 2. Example of submitted task with (positive) feedback

Moodle allows group submissions; when the teacher grades the tasks all the elements of the group are notified, receive the same classification and can access the teacher’s feedback, which can be provided in different formats: writing on the submitted task, as in Figure 2, or directly in Moodle boxes, as a general comment or in each rubric (see Figure 3).

Table 1: Assessment grid for tasks.

Criterion	Description
Understanding of Mathematical Concepts	4 - Demonstrates a deep and correct understanding of mathematical concepts, without errors.
	3 - Understands mathematical concepts well, with minor errors.
	2 - Understands the basic concepts but makes a few mistakes that do not seriously jeopardise the work.
	1 - Partially understands the concepts but makes several mistakes that affect the accuracy of the work.
	0 - Shows no understanding of mathematical concepts, with many errors.
Task organisation and presentation	4 - The work is very well organised, with a clear, logical and easy-to-follow presentation.
	3 - The work is well organised and the presentation is clear, with minor improvements possible.
	2 - The work is organised, but the presentation can be confusing in some parts.
	1 - The work is poorly organised and the presentation is difficult to follow.
	0 - The work is disorganised and the presentation is very confusing.
Justification and Argumentation	4 - Justifies all answers with logical and well-founded arguments.
	3 - Justifies most answers with solid arguments.
	2 - Justifies some answers, but with arguments that may be weak or incomplete.
	1 - Justifies few answers, with insufficient arguments.
	0 - Don't justify their answers or their arguments are invalid.
Use of mathematical language and representation	4 - Uses mathematical representations and language correctly and effectively.
	3 - Uses mathematical representations and language correctly, with minor flaws.
	2 - Uses some mathematical representations and/or language, but makes mistakes in some of them.
	1 - Uses few mathematical representations and/or language and makes many mistakes.
	0 - Does not use mathematical representations and/or language or uses them incorrectly.

Compreensão dos Conceitos Matemáticos	Não demonstra compreensão dos conceitos matemáticos, com muitos erros. 0 pontos	Compreende parcialmente os conceitos, comete vários erros que afetam a precisão do trabalho. 1 ponto	Compreende os conceitos básicos, mas comete alguns erros que não comprometem gravemente o trabalho. 2 pontos	Compreende bem os conceitos matemáticos, com erros menores. 3 pontos	Demonstra uma compreensão profunda e correta dos conceitos matemáticos, sem erros. 4 pontos	Tentar corrigir os erros
Organização e Apresentação da tarefa	O trabalho está desorganizado e a apresentação é muito confusa. 0 pontos	O trabalho está mal organizado e a apresentação é difícil de seguir. 1 ponto	O trabalho está organizado, mas a apresentação pode ser confusa em algumas partes. 2 pontos	O trabalho está bem organizado e a apresentação é clara, com pequenas melhorias possíveis. 3 pontos	O trabalho está muito bem organizado, com uma apresentação clara, lógica e fácil de seguir. 4 pontos	

Figure 3. Example of the evaluation grid

2.2 Peer assessment

As mentioned above, students were assigned to groups which were randomly changed every four working sessions, that is three times along the semester. After these four sessions each student evaluated themselves and their peers regarding their performance on the work developed together. Again, rubrics were used to normalize the assessment results.

Table 2. Rubrics for peer assessment.

Criterion	Description
Participation and involvement	4 - Always participates extremely active and enthusiastically in all tasks.
	3 - Participates actively and enthusiastically in solving tasks.
	2 - Participates in tasks regularly, but without much enthusiasm
	1 - Participates rarely in tasks and discussions and with little enthusiasm.
	0 - Does not participate in tasks or get involved in discussions.
Collaboration in solving tasks	4 - Always co-operates with colleagues, helping and encouraging them to solve all tasks.
	3 - Almost always co-operates with colleagues in solving tasks.
	2 - Occasionally co-operates with colleagues.
	1 - Co-operates rarely and only when asked.
	0 - Does not co-operate with colleagues in the group.
Respect for colleagues	4 - Always respects colleagues' opinions and shows empathy.
	3 - Often respects the opinions of colleagues.
	2 - Occasionally respects colleagues' opinions.

	1 - Rarely respects colleagues' opinions.
	0 - Does not respect colleagues' opinions.
Responsibility	4 - Always meets deadlines and fulfils assigned tasks.
	3 - Frequently meets deadlines and fulfils assigned tasks.
	2 - Occasionally fulfils the deadlines and tasks assigned to them.
	1 - Seldom fulfils the deadlines and tasks assigned to them.
	0 - Does not fulfil the deadlines and tasks assigned to them.

When answering peer assessment, the students were reminded of the following rule: "You must assess the performance of your classmates and your own performance. If you fail to do so, your grade in this component will be penalised by 30%. Be FAIR AND RESPONSIBLE in your assessment because this grade influences the final classification on the course". Nevertheless, they tended not to punish their peers, and if they did, the penalties were very soft.

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7
S1	4/3/4/4	4/4/4/4	3/3/4/4	3/3/4/4	3/3/4/4	3/3/4/4	3/3/4/4
S2	3/3/4/4	4/4/4/4	4/4/4/4	2/3/4/4	2/3/4/4	0/1/4/4	2/3/4/4
S3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S4	4/4/4/4	4/4/4/4	4/4/4/4	2/2/4/4	4/4/4/4	1/1/4/4	4/4/4/4
S5	3/4/4/4	3/4/4/4	3/4/4/4	3/4/4/4	3/4/4/4	1/1/4/4	3/4/4/4
S6	4/4/4/4	3/3/4/4	4/4/4/4	3/2/4/3	3/2/4/3	1/2/4/3	3/3/4/3
S7	4/3/4/4	4/3/4/4	4/3/4/4	3/2/4/4	3/2/4/4	0/0/4/1	3/2/4/4

Figure 4: An example of a peer assessment evaluation of the four criteria, where student S3 did not answer

To assess their peers, students analyse the assessment criteria in more depth and, also, critically reflect on their own work. Receiving and giving feedback among peers promotes individual and social development, giving them the tools to critically analyse their work and that of others in the future, to communicate feedback in a constructive way, and to accept and incorporate the opinions of others into their work.

2.3 Assessment

A light version of continuous assessment was used in this Calculus course consisting of various elements collected throughout the semester, namely:

- Assignments completed during class throughout the semester – 12%;
- Peer assessment and self-assessment– 8%;
- Two online tests– 15% each;
- Written test in the last week of the term– 50%.

The online tests were conducted on Moodle using Multiple Choice Questions (MCQ).

MCQ can be graded quickly and objectively (Klufa, 2015), especially with automated systems. They allow for a wide range of topics to be tested within a single exam and scoring is less subjective compared to open-ended questions. With MCQ multiple versions of a test can be created easily, ensuring consistency in assessment, which is an asset when assessing hundreds of students. However, students can sometimes guess the correct answers, which can affect the reliability of the test, but (Klufa, 2015) states that the probability of scoring 50% or more in this kind of test is 0,011839.

Open ended questions (OED) complement MCQ: they can assess students' deep understanding and ability to articulate complex ideas; they encourage critical thinking and the ability to construct coherent arguments; students can express their knowledge in their own words, which can be more reflective of their understanding. Written exams allow for creative responses and problem-solving as OEQ aim to elicit detailed and comprehensive responses that provide insight into students' thought processes.

A written test was carried out in the last week of the term using OEQ, "giving the students the opportunity to provide different answers" (Bingölbali & Bingölbali, 2021).

In our opinion these four elements used in assessment are enough to classify students, despite the subjectivity inherent in an evaluation process.

2.4 Games used

Gamification in education has been shown to create a stimulating learning environment, encouraging active participation and collaboration among students. Some examples of games used in Education are presented in (Noda, Shiotsuki, & Nakao, 2019).

As referred to in (Radzi, Ying, Abidin, & Ahmad, 2020) "One of the specialties of board game is engagement and connectivity by enforcing active interaction between players during play session. Furthermore, board game enables players to foster a reflective environment for learning a certain knowledge context and enables player to creatively solve problem in the game world." Besides, board games introduce an element of fun and competition, which promotes motivation and can lead to deeper conceptual understanding and better retention of information.

The games used in our Calculus classes were "Guess who" played with the whole class and "The mysterious rule", about functions of one variable and their graphs; in the study of inverse trigonometric functions the game "Math Twins" was played and on antiderivatives we used "The antiderivatives box". These games were designed for group play, promoting teamwork and communication. This collaborative aspect can enhance learning by allowing students to discuss strategies, explain their reasoning, and learn from each other, turning classrooms in active learning spaces. The description of these games can be found in (Oliveira, 2024).

3 Discussion

3.1 Students' opinions

At the end of the semester, we asked students to complete an anonymous online survey ("Your opinion matters. Help us improve the course") with the purpose of evaluating the effectiveness of the teaching strategies implemented in our Calculus course.

The survey results show that students valued collaborative activities, such as group work and peer assessment, because they promoted a deeper understanding of the subjects and more active participation from everyone. One student wrote "In Group work (TPA), we can develop communication and teamwork skills and at the same time understand the subject better." Students also highlight the added benefit of staying up-to-date with the study of the taught topics and assisting in organizing their study.

The use of Vevox was particularly appreciated in the theoretical lectures, as it promoted real-time interaction and immediate feedback. One of the answers referred that "it created an effective learning environment".

In addition, the online tests and group work provided opportunities for continuous assessment, allowing students to track their progress throughout the semester. Despite some students not liking online tests due to

multiple-choice questions, overall, students appreciated the assessment method used because it included various components.

3.2 Analysis of the assessment results

In recent years, we have been teaching the Calculus course to first-year students, consistently implementing various strategies to engage students in the learning process. The undergraduate programs that include Calculus courses underwent changes in the 2023/24 academic year, which is when we began to deploy the methods discussed in this article.

By comparing the data for the last two years, we can observe a significant reduction in the number of students who did not participate in any form of assessment, decreasing from 12.03% to 6.85%. Achieving this reduction was one of our primary goals.

At the same time, pass rates increased both relative to the total number of students enrolled in the course and to the number of students assessed. In 2023/24, out of a total of 507 students, 53.85% passed, corresponding to 61.21% of those that were assessed. This year, 2024/25, 67.32% of the 511 students enrolled in the course passed, that is, 72.27% of the students who were assessed.

Another noteworthy aspect, supporting our belief that this methodology produces more lasting learning outcomes, is the increase in the number of students passing the resit exam. Indeed, considering only the total number of assessed students, given a similar pass rate for the regular exam (58.7% in 2023/24 and 59.53% in 2024/25), the pass rate for the resit exam raised from 2.51% to 12.74%.

In 2023/24, we implemented the methodology described in this article for the first time. There were still many aspects to refine, particularly in how tasks were submitted and assessed, in peer evaluations, and in making small adjustments to communication and resources provided to students. Additionally, the teaching team in 2024/25 was more cohesive and having a unified perspective on modern education. These factors may contribute to explain the improved results of 2024/25.

4 Conclusion

The implementation of innovative teaching strategies in the Calculus course for first-year students has shown promising results. By incorporating active learning techniques, peer assessment, and diverse evaluation methods, we have observed a significant improvement in student engagement and performance. The reduction in the number of students not participating in assessments and the increase in pass rates, both during regular and resit exam periods, highlight the effectiveness of these methodologies.

The challenges faced in the initial year of implementation, such as the quality of student submissions and the consistency of peer assessments, provided valuable insights for refining our approach. The improvements seen in the subsequent year, particularly in the robustness of the methods and the cohesiveness of the teaching team, further validate the positive impact of these strategies.

Overall, this study demonstrates that a combination of interactive learning tools, structured group work, and varied assessment techniques can significantly enhance the learning experience and outcomes for students in STEM disciplines. These findings offer valuable insights for educators seeking to adopt innovative approaches to foster deeper learning and improve student success.

A detailed analysis of the results of the survey and a discussion of the assessment results can be found in (Nolasco, Oliveira, & Vettori, to be published).

References

- Bingölbali, E., & Bingölbali, F. (2021). An Examination of Open-Ended Mathematics Questions' Affordances. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(4), pp. 1-16. doi:10.29329/ijpe.2021.366.1
- Boud, D. (2010). *Assessment 2020: Seven propositions for assessment reform in higher*. Sydney: Australian Learning and Teaching Council. Obtido de www.assessmentfutures.com
- Brookhart, S. M. (2013). *How to Create and Use Rubrics for Formative Assessment and Grading*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Wenderoth, M. P., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., & Jordt, H. (12 de May de 2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. (B. Alberts, Ed.) *Psychological and Cognitive Sciences*, 111(23), pp. 8410-8415. doi:10.1073/pnas.1319030111
- Klufa, J. (2015). Multiple Choice Question Tests – Advantages and Disadvantages. *Mathematics and Computers in Sciences and Industry*, pp. 91-97.
- Noda, S., Shiotsuki, K., & Nakao, M. (2019). The effectiveness of intervention with board games: a systematic review. *BioPsychoSocial Medicine*, pp. 1-21. doi:10.1186/s13030-019-0164-1
- Nolasco, A. P., Oliveira, M. P., & Vettori, P. (to be published). Strategies to improve student engagement: comparison of assessment results and student feedback. *END2025*.
- Oliveira, M. (2024). GAMES AND CALCULUS . *Education and New Developments 2024 (END2024)* (pp. 203-207). Porto: Mafalda Carmo. doi:10.36315/2024v1end043
- Radzi, S. B., Ying, T. Y., Abidin, M. Z., & Ahmad, P. A. (2020). The effectiveness of board game towards soft skills development for higher education. *Ilkogretim Online - Elementary Education Online*, 19(2), pp. 94-106. doi:10.17051/ilkonline.2020.02.111
- Springer, L., Stanne, M. E., & Donovan, S. S. (1999). Effects of Small-Group Learning on Undergraduates in Science, Mathematics, Engineering, and Technology: A Meta-Analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 69(1), pp. 21-51. doi:10.3102/00346543069001021